

SYSTEM OF AXIOMS OF RIEMANNIAN GEOMETRY

Hamdamova Durdona Xayrullo kizi**Kokan State Pedagogical Institute, faculty of physics and mathematics, 2nd year
student, department of mathematics and informatics****Jorayev Shukurjon****Scientific supervisor****www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10566608**

Abstract. In this paper we present a Riemannian framework for smoothing data that are constrained to live in $P(n)$, the space of symmetric positive-definite matrices of order n . We start by giving the differential geometry of $P(n)$, with a special emphasis on $P(3)$, considered at a level of detail far greater than heretofore. We then use the harmonic map and minimal immersion theories to construct three flows that drive a noisy field of symmetric positive-definite data into a smooth one. The harmonic map flow is equivalent to the heat flow or isotropic linear diffusion which smooths data everywhere. A modification of the harmonic flow leads to a Perona-Malik like flow which is a selective smoother that preserves edges. The minimal immersion flow gives rise to a nonlinear system of coupled diffusion equations with anisotropic diffusivity. Some preliminary numerical results are presented for synthetic DT-MRI data.

Keywords: Symmetric positive-definite matrices, Riemannian metric, Laplace-Beltrami, Regularization of DT-MRI data.

INTRODUCTION

In the last few years, there has been a revival in the use of differential-geometric tools for various problems in applied mathematics. For instance, differential geometric methods have been successfully used in control theory, in mechanics, in nonlinear optimization, and recently image processing and computer vision. From these applications, it has become clear that geometric methods offer not only the advantage of formulating problems posed on manifold in an intrinsic and elegant manner, but also they give insights on how to built robust numerical methods for solving them. In the field of image processing, the problem of regularizing noisy data defined on non-flat surfaces has been handled with two formalisms which operate on the space of embedding maps between Riemannian manifolds: the harmonic map and minimal immersion flows.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

At the advent of Diffusion-Tensor Magnetic Resonance Imaging (DT-MRI), matrix-valued data and more specifically symmetric positive-definite data sets it produces have attracted an increasing attention. We note that for this imaging modality, a symmetric positive definite matrix is estimated at each point of the imaging volume. As a result, there has been a renewed interest in the study of the differential-geometric properties of the space of symmetric positive-definite matrices and in processing measured data that are constrained to live on this space. It is widely known that processing methods for vector- and matrix-valued data that are based on scalar-valued data processing procedure present several shortcomings. The situation is even worse if we are, as in DT-MRI data, dealing with nonlinearly constrained matrix-valued data. The aim of this paper is to develop a novel framework for denoising symmetric positive-definite fields based on the differential geometry of the underlying

manifold. More specifically, we extend the harmonic map and minimal immersion formalisms to the regularization of tensor-valued images like DT-MRI.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The space of symmetric positive-definite matrices is probably the most important set of matrices that one deals with in various branches of mathematics, numerical analysis, physics, mechanics, probability, and other fundamental and engineering sciences. Because of its importance, this set of matrices has been analyzed from several perspectives.

As stated previously, the set of symmetric positive-definite matrices, as a Riemannian manifold, is the most studied example of manifolds of nonpositive curvature. However, to the best of our knowledge, no explicit form of quantities like the metric tensor, Christoffel symbols and curvature, and operators such as gradient, divergence and intrinsic Laplacian, have been given previously. In this section, we will use the Kronecker product and the duplication matrix introduced in the previous section to derive the explicit forms of these quantities and operators.

The geodesics $P : [a, b] \rightarrow P(n)$ of $P(n)$ equipped with the Riemannian metric (11) satisfy the second-order differential equation

$$P'' - P'P^{-1}P' = 0,$$

and the geodesic emanating from $P_0 \in P(n)$ in the direction of $S \in S(n)$

Diffusion Tensor Magnetic Resonance Imaging (DT-MRI) is a relatively new modality that provides a non-invasive probe into the microstructure of materials. It is based on the principle of MRI which measures the displacements of particles undergoing Brownian motion inside the material sample to be explored. In the biological context, as water is a major constituent of biological tissues, the particles of interest are water molecules. The main biomedical applications of diffusion tensor imaging are in brain, muscles and heart imaging. Nowadays, DT-MRI has become an important tool in some clinical applications. For example, diffusion-tensor brain images are being used to infer the architecture of the brain by the establishment of the white matter connectivity map, and to obtain information about some brain pathologies. Under the assumption that the probability density of water displacement is a zero-mean trivariate Gaussian distribution, measurements of diffusion-weighted MRI yield, at each voxel of the imaging domain, a symmetric tensor with six independent components. This tensor characterizes the diffusivity of water in any 3-dimensional direction. Such diffusivities are directly related to the local structure of biological tissue, in particular the distribution and orientation of cell membranes. We refer the interested reader to [6, 30, 38] and the references therein for the concepts, principles, and applications of diffusion tensor imaging.

In this section we start by briefly reviewing the basics of the theories of harmonic maps and minimal immersions which are special cases of maps between Riemannian manifolds. The theory of minimal surfaces and more generally of minimal immersions is one of the most studied subjects in differential geometry. Since the very early stage of the theory it was clear that there is a strong link between minimality and harmonicity. Indeed, Eells and Simpson [17] proved that an isometric immersion is minimal if and only if it is a harmonic map. We then describe the harmonic map and minimal immersion flows that we use for the regularization of DT-MRI data.

CONCLUSION

We believe that the Riemannian frame- work presented in this paper is a significant contribution in the field of regularization of tensor fields. It is interesting to compare the performance of the methods presented here with that of other methods on real DT-MRI data sets.

References:

1. Aja-Fernández, S., de Luis García, R., Tao, D., Li, X. (eds.): Ten- sors in Image Processing and Computer Vision, Advances in Pat- tern Recognition. Springer, Berlin (2019)
2. Andai, A.: Information geometry in quantum mechanics. PhD the- sis, Department for Analysis, Budapest University of Technology and Economics (2013) in Hungarian
3. Anderson, D., Hoffman, D., Henke, C., Thomas, E.L.: Periodic area-minimizing surfaces in block copolymers. *Nature* 334, 598– 601 (2018)
4. Andersson, S., Hyde, S.T., Larsson, K., Lidin, S.: Minimal sur- faces and structures: From inorganic and metal crystals to cell membranes and biopolymers. *Chem. Rev.* 88, 221–242 (2018)

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY